

GeoLink R Package

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Summary

GeoLink R package allows merging publicly available geospatial indicators with georeferenced survey data. The latter can contain lat/long geocoordinates or an administrative identifier with corresponding shapefile. The package facilitates: geospatial data download, shapefile tessellation, zonal statistics calculation, and spatial joining of geospatial with unit level data – and can be used to

1) Link household characteristics measured in surveys with geospatial indicators; 2) Calculate indicator values per pixel covered by a tessellated grid in which a household is located; 3) Calculate zonal statistics for a user-defined shapefile and link to survey data. GeoLink complements ‘Povmap’ and ‘EMDI’ R packages.

KEYWORDS: social statistics, geospatial indicator, administrative unit, household survey, poverty mapping

1. Extended Abstract

GeoLink is a new R package that aims to improve the user experience regarding the preparation of high resolution geospatial/remote sensing indicators and their integration with other sources of georeferenced data such as household surveys. GeoLink can be used as a companion to the EMDI and Povmap R packages – which enables the estimation of regionally disaggregated indicators using Small Area Estimation (SAE) methods and includes tools for processing, assessing, and presenting the results. As such, GeoLink simplifies and makes more efficient the various geospatial data input routes and so acts as a support package for those end users that rely on using such data in their analyses. Whilst the primary intended use case of GeoLink is to calculate geospatial indicator values within administrative unit level data, if required the package can also be used to tessellate a grid (i.e. create a shapefile). Zonal statistics can then be calculated for each grid, which can be matched to household locations. The package will download a variety of geospatial indicator data to user specification, calculate zonal statistics for these, and spatially join the geospatial data with unit level data. Because of the range of geospatial indicators that are incorporated into GeoLink, the package can be applied in broad economic/policy analyses targeted at specific settings and so has relevance across many different user applications. Geospatial indicators currently incorporated into the package include:

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- Climate Hazards Group Infra-Red Precipitation with Station data (CHIRPS) precipitation data from 1981 onwards (Funk et al. 2014)
- Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) future climate scenarios global climate projection data for years 2015-2100 (O'Neill et al. 2016)
- European Space Agency (ESA) WorldCover cropland dataset for the year 2020 (Zanaga et al. 2022)
- High Resolution Electricity Access (HREA) data for 115 developing countries for the year 2015 (Min et al. 2024)
- Impact Observatory (IO) annual Land Use Land Cover (LULC, 9-class) V2 data from 2017-2023 (Karra et al. 2021)
- Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) Vegetation Indices v6.1 data from 2000 onwards (Didan and Munoz, 2019)
- Open Street Map (OSM) points of interest data (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2025)
- Sentinel-5P pollution high-resolution imagery data for period May 2018 to present (ESA, 2022)
- Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) elevation data hole-filled seamless V4 with near global coverage for year 2000 (Reuter et al. 2007)
- Terraclimate temperature, precipitation, and other climate and weather data for global terrestrial surfaces from 1958 onwards (Abatzoglou et al. 2018)
- Visible and Infrared Imaging Suite (VIIRS) night-time lights data from 2012 onwards (Elvidge et al. 2021)
- WorldClim climate temperature, precipitation, solar radiation, wind speed, water vapour pressure data for years 1970-2000 (Fick and Hijmans, 2017)
- WorldPop buildings pattern and metrics for 51 developing countries for the year 2020/1 (Dooley et al. 2021)
- WorldPop human population estimates for individual countries from the year 2000 to 2020 (Stevens et al 2015, Lloyd et al. 2017, Lloyd et al. 2019, Bondarenko et al. 2020, Nieves et al, 2020ab), including:
 - Built settlement constrained and UN adjusted population estimates for the year 2020
 - More recent population estimates using more accurate bespoke methods for specific Sub-Saharan African countries (WorldPop Open Population Repository, 2024)
- World Bank OpenCellId global cellular tower map for the year 2020 (OpenCellID Project contributors, 2025)

The primary purpose of the GeoLink package is to facilitate semi-automated user download and merge of various geospatial data into geocoded surveys. The Geolink package extracts data into a shapefile provided by the user. An added service for tessellating/ gridding a shapefile is also provided for users that require such data, and for further analytics that require equal area zonal statistics. Shapefile estimates at the grid or native polygon level are a permitted final output. However, a geocoded survey with estimates of geospatial dataset values (e.g. rainfall, night-time lights) is the end goal if the user chooses. The package will merge shapefile polygons (either gridded or native polygons) with the location of the survey units (e.g. rainfall estimates for the locations of the units within the survey could be returned). The package is also set up for Stata users, allowing the user to pass file paths for the household survey.

We present the new functionalities of the GeoLink package, as a companion to the Povmap and EMDI packages. These functionalities include options for incorporating various open source geospatial data, user friendly output options, and a convenient wrapper for Stata users.

This package can simplify the application of SAE methods by easy input of geospatial indicator variables. The package is, to the best of our knowledge, the first R geospatial package that supports the user with a full input workflow prior to estimation of complex, non-linear indicators of poverty. GeoLink can also be applied in broader economic/policy analyses targeted at specific settings. Another important feature is that since GeoLink makes the application of geospatial indicators to SAE methods in R very simple, it also has the potential to close the gap between theoretical advances in SAE and their application by practitioners. Additional geospatial indicators will be integrated in future versions of the package.

2. Acknowledgements

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3. Biography

Christopher T Lloyd is a Data Scientist at WorldPop, University of Southampton - leading production of geospatial datasets using open source methods for input to human population models. He has a particular interest in the application of machine learning to classify and detect buildings. Chris produces training materials and co-supervises PhD research.

Ifeanyi Edochie is a Data Scientist in the World Bank's Institutions Department. His work has focused on providing solutions to analytical problems around poverty mapping and the use of 'geospatial' in household surveys and other georeferenced data objects. He is developing a knowledge platform/repository for all governance related data for the World Bank's government counterparts.

Daylan AS Gomez is a Consultant at the World Bank's Data for Goals Team. His responsibilities encompass household survey management, as well as integration of geospatial indicators into geocoded surveys. His work has facilitated liaison between the World Bank and UNICEF in the estimation of child poverty.

Diana Jaganjac is a Data Scientist with expertise in geospatial analytics and data engineering. Her work has focused on providing innovative solutions across international geoscience companies and startups. She now works for the World Bank, developing both software for geospatial science applications and machine learning models for poverty mapping and analysis.

Josh Merfeld is an Associate Professor at the KDI School of Public Policy and Management, South Korea. His research and teaching interests include development, applied microeconometrics, agriculture, poverty, and the environment. He is particularly interested in using new data sources and new empirical methods to improve our understanding of a wide range of outcomes, especially SDGs.

David Newhouse is a Senior Economist in the World Bank's Development Economics Data Group, and an elected fellow of the Institute of Labor Economics and the International Statistical Institute. His work has focused on economic measurement, including integrating survey data with non-traditional data, and analysis related to poverty and jobs in developing countries.

Luciano Perfetti is a PhD candidate at the University of Southampton, researching the use of geospatial and other alternative data sources in small-area estimation, with special emphasis on poverty mapping. Luciano has experience using statistical and machine learning methods to improve public policies with international organisations and government agencies.

Nikos Tzavidis is Professor of Statistical Methodology at the University of Southampton. His research focuses on topics in small area estimation, outlier robust estimation, quantile regression, applications of machine learning to official statistics and the integration of survey and geospatial data.

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